

A dynamic momentum power method for the neutron diffusion equation

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ABSTRACT

In this work we formulate a dynamic momentum method applied to the neutron diffusion equation. This is a generalization of the existing method in the literature and provides a robust and scalable solution strategy for computing the multiplication factor of the two-group neutron diffusion equation. We validate our methodology with several 2D and 3D numerical tests, including the IAEA2D benchmark. All of our tests show that the dynamic momentum iterations are mesh independent, and thus this strategy combined with a scalable solver for the source problem yields a scalable solution strategy for the generalized eigenvalue problem with linear complexity in practice.

Keywords: Dynamic Momentum Power Method, Finite Elements Method, Neutronics

1. INTRODUCTION

The multi-group neutron diffusion equation quantizes the steady state equation of neutron flux balance into a finite number of energy groups. The most commonly studied one is the two-group equation, which considers a fast group with higher energy, and a thermal group with lower energy. In the steady state form, the neutron diffusion equation includes the multiplication factor k , which scales the fission source term in order to balance the neutron generation and loss rates. This leads to a generalized eigenvalue problem, which can be numerically approximated with a discretization strategy, and then solved with numerical methods.

Finding the multiplication factor k can be recast as computing the smallest eigenvalue of the multi-group equation, and thus the power method [1] yields an effective strategy to do such a computation. Indeed, this method is used in practice by some solvers of the neutron diffusion equation, such as [2]. The power method yields linear convergence [1], which can yield high iteration counts, and it can additionally present deterioration as the problem size increases. This has motivated the use of acceleration strategies to improve the convergence of the power method, such as Anderson and Chebyshev [3]. Anderson acceleration provides a good performance, but has the drawback that it requires an increasing amount of memory to be robust, and can further yield convergence to other eigenvalues instead of the desired one [4]. On the other hand, Chebyshev acceleration for the power method requires a prior estimation of the problem spectrum. As an improvement, it was proposed in [4] to use instead a Dynamic Momentum Power Method (DMPM), which yields robust behavior with a simple 2 term recursion without any prior knowledge of the spectrum. This method has proved convergence for symmetric matrices.

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In this work, we extend the DMPM from [4] to generalized eigenvalue problems and propose solving the two-group neutron diffusion equation in 2D and 3D using that method to test its effectiveness. Our formulation is based on a Finite Elements Method (FEM) discretization of the equations, which has been shown theoretically to converge for this problem [5], and all numerical tests have been implemented using FEniCSx [6] and SLEPc [7]. Our results show that the resulting method is robust and scalable, yielding time reductions with respect to using SLEPc of up to a 70% in 2D and 90% in 3D, with lower memory requirements as well.

2. NEUTRON DIFFUSION EQUATION

We consider a two group neutron diffusion formulation for the fast and thermal energy group denoted by $\phi_1(x)$ and $\phi_2(x)$ respectively. In a given bounded domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^d, d \in \{2, 3\}$ the equations are given by the following:

$$-\nabla \cdot (D_1 \nabla \phi_1) + (\Sigma_{a1} + \Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2}) \phi_1 = \frac{1}{k} \left(\nu_1 \Sigma_{f1} \phi_1 + \nu_2 \Sigma_{f2} \phi_2 \right) \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (1a)$$

$$-\nabla \cdot (D_2 \nabla \phi_2) + \Sigma_{a2} \phi_2 - \Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2} \phi_1 = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (1b)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial n} = -\alpha \phi_1, \quad \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial n} = -\alpha \phi_2 \quad \text{in } \partial\Omega, \quad (1c)$$

where D_1 and D_2 are the diffusion coefficients, Σ_{a1} and Σ_{a2} the macroscopic absorption cross-sections, $\Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2}$ the macroscopic down scattering cross sections, Σ_{f1}, Σ_{f2} the macroscopic fission cross-sections, ν_1 and ν_2 are dimensionless and represent the average number of neutrons produced by fission. Each of these values for the fast and thermal energy groups respectively. Lastly, α is the boundary albedo parameter. The largest value k that satisfies the equation above is known as the multiplication factor. In block form, system (1) reads as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ -\Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{A}_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{k} \begin{bmatrix} \nu_1 \Sigma_{f1} f_1 & \nu_2 \Sigma_{f2} f_2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_1 = -\nabla \cdot D_1 \nabla + (\Sigma_{a1} + \Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2}) \mathbf{I}$ and $\mathbf{A}_2 = -\nabla \cdot D_2 \nabla + \Sigma_{a2} \mathbf{I}$, with \mathbf{I} the identity operator. We then define the operators

$$\mathcal{L} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ -\Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2} \mathbf{I} & \mathbf{A}_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{R} = \begin{bmatrix} \nu_1 \Sigma_{f1} f_1 & \nu_2 \Sigma_{f2} f_2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

to write the generalized eigenvalue problem (1) as

$$\mathcal{R} \phi = k \mathcal{L} \phi. \quad (4)$$

Since the operator \mathcal{L} is always non-singular [5] the system can be transformed into a standard eigenvalue problem

$$\mathcal{L}^{-1} \mathcal{R} \phi = k \phi. \quad (5)$$

In other words, the problem of finding k reduces to computing the dominant eigenvalue of the operator $\mathcal{L}^{-1} \mathcal{R}$. We discretize both operators with FEM using H^1 conforming piecewise linear functions, leading to the following generalized eigenvalue problem,

$$R \phi_h = k_h L \phi_h, \quad (6)$$

where R and L are real matrices, ϕ_h is the discrete vector that approximates ϕ and k_h is the approximation of k . This approximation has been shown to converge to the continuous one with optimal convergence rates [5].

3. DYNAMIC MOMENTUM POWER METHOD

In this section we review the classic power method and show how to add dynamic momentum to it as in [4]. We then show how to extend this method to our context.

3.1. Classic Power Method

The power method is an iterative algorithm used to compute the largest eigenvalue of an eigenvalue problem, which is assumed to be a real number. It has been shown that this is indeed the case for the multi-group equation [5]. The power iteration is fundamentally based on the Rayleigh quotient.

In the generalized power iteration the method starts with an arbitrary vector v_0 , and repeatedly applies the Rayleigh quotient associated to that vector, until the sequence converges. The Rayleigh quotient is defined as

$$\rho(v) = \frac{v^T R v}{v^T L v}. \quad (7)$$

At each iteration i , we approximate the eigenvalue and eigenvector as

$$\lambda_i = \rho(v_i), \quad \text{and} \quad v_{i+1} = L^{-1} R v_i. \quad (8)$$

The sequence $\{\lambda_i\}_i$ converges to the largest eigenvalue λ_1 (i.e. k), and $\{v_i\}_i$ converges to its associated eigenvector $\phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2)$, where we highlight that we have dropped the 'h' subindex to avoid excessive notation. To use this method it is required that the multiplicity of the first eigenvalue is 1, and the convergence rate would be the quotient

$$r = \left| \frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} \right|. \quad (9)$$

3.2. Dynamic Momentum Power Method

As presented in [4], the power method for real matrices can be accelerated by introducing a momentum term β and then modifying the original problem into the following augmented one:

$$(L^{-1}R)_\beta = \begin{bmatrix} L^{-1}R & -\beta I \\ I & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

The value of β that optimizes the asymptotic convergence rate of the power method was proven to be [4]

$$\beta = \frac{\lambda_2^2}{4}, \quad (11)$$

where λ_2 is the second largest eigenvalue. Naturally, this is difficult to compute in practice, which motivated the proposal of a dynamic update method for the β parameter. The dynamic momentum method estimates the value of the momentum parameter β adaptively at each iteration. At iteration i we define the i -th residual $d_i := \|R x_i - \lambda_i L x_i\|$ and consider the values of the residuals from the last two iterations d_{i+1}, d_i to compute ρ_i ,

$$\rho_i = \frac{d_{i+1}}{d_i}. \quad (12)$$

The optimal convergence rate is

$$\frac{r}{1 - \sqrt{1 - r^2}}, \quad r = \left| \frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} \right|. \quad (13)$$

At each iteration, we compute an optimal approximation of r_{i+1} by using ρ_i . For this, we solve the following equation,

$$\rho_i = \frac{r_{i+1}}{1 - \sqrt{1 - r_{i+1}^2}}, \quad (14)$$

which gives

$$r_{i+1} = \frac{2\rho_i}{1 + \rho_i^2}. \quad (15)$$

Lastly, let be $\lambda_{2,i}$ the approximation of λ_2 at iteration i and $\lambda_{1,i}$ the approximation of λ_1 at iteration i . We can obtain $\lambda_{2,i}$ with $r_i\lambda_{1,i}$ so that at each iteration, we use the following momentum parameter

$$\beta_i = \frac{\lambda_{1,i}^2 r_i^2}{4}. \quad (16)$$

This gives us Algorithm 1, based on the algorithm from [4], which we refer to as Generalized Dynamic Momentum Power Method (GDMPM). We introduced the necessary steps to solve the generalized problem, and denoted $\lambda_{1,i} = \lambda_i$ for simplicity.

Algorithm 1 Generalized Dynamic Momentum Power Method.

Input $R \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, L \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}, v_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Set $h_0 = \|v_0\|_L, x_0 = h_0^{-1}v_0$

Set $v_1 = L^{-1}Rv_0$

for $i \in \{0, 1\}$ **do**

Set $h_{i+1} = \|v_{i+1}\|_L$ and $x_{i+1} = h_{i+1}^{-1}v_{i+1}$

Set $v_{i+1} = L^{-1}Rx_{i+1}$

Set $\lambda_{i+1} = x_{i+1}^T Rx_{i+1}$ and $d_{i+1} = \|Rx_{i+1} - \lambda_{i+1}Lx_{i+1}\|$

STOP if $d_{i+1} < \text{TOL}$

end for

Set $r_2 = \min\{d_2/d_1, 1\}$

for $i \geq 2$ **do**

Set $\beta_i = \lambda_i^2 r_i^2 / 4$

Set $v_{i+1} = L^{-1}Rx_i$

Set $u_{i+1} = v_{i+1} - (\beta_i/h_i)x_{i-1}$

Set $h_{i+1} = \|u_{i+1}\|_L$ and $x_{i+1} = h_{i+1}^{-1}u_{i+1}$

Set $\lambda_{i+1} = x_{i+1}^T Rx_{i+1}$ and $d_{i+1} = \|Rx_{i+1} - \lambda_{i+1}Lx_{i+1}\|$

Update $\rho_i = \min\{d_{i+1}/d_i, 1\}$ and $r_{i+1} = 2\rho_i / (1 + \rho_i^2)$

STOP if $d_{i+1} < \text{TOL}$

end for

return λ_{i+1}, v_{i+1}

3.3. Algorithm complexity and expected behavior

As mentioned in the introduction, one fundamental advantage of the GDMPM is that it has a very small memory footprint, and relies only on the solution of a linear system (step $v_{i+1} = L^{-1}Rx_i$ in Algorithm 1).

This means that the overall expected complexity of the method is given by vector operations, which is linear, plus the complexity of the linear solver. For our work, we note that system (2) is elliptic for some values of $\Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2}$ [5], which enables the use of an efficient GMRES algorithm [8] preconditioned with an Algebraic Multigrid method [9]. This results in an overall linear complexity for Algorithm 1. The only problem that could hinder convergence is that the number of GDMPM iterations could increase with the problem size, which we show not to happen in the tests considered in Section 4.

4. NUMERICAL TESTS

To computationally validate the theoretical results, we run simulations using a unit square, a unit cube and the IAEA 2D benchmark. For each of these domains, we computed the solution time (i.e. wall clock time) for varying problem sizes in order to study the scalability of the method and to additionally compare the GDMPM with a more traditional use of SLEPc with default settings, which implies the Krylov-Schur solver. This is an Arnoldi iteration with restart [7]. Given the matrix structure, we use a generalized non-hermitian solver given by the GNHEP solver type. For these tests we use a relative tolerance of 10^{-7} to solve the linear system, and a tolerance of 10^{-6} for the GDMPM, computed as the ℓ^2 norm of the residual $r(k_h, x) = |R\phi_h - k_h L\phi_h|$.

The code used to run the numerical tests can be found in [10].

4.1. Unit Square test

We solved the problem in a unit square geometry for 6 different mesh sizes. We use Robin boundary conditions as in (1c) with $\alpha = 0.4692$, together with the coefficients shown in Table I.

Table I. Unit square test, parameters used.

D_1	D_2	$\Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2}$	Σ_{a1}	Σ_{a2}	$\nu\Sigma_{f1}$	$\nu\Sigma_{f2}$
1.0	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.1

After running the simulations, we obtained the execution times for each mesh shown in Table II for increasing Degrees of Freedom (DoFs). We highlight that our method yields a reduction in the solution time of up to a 90% in the largest problem.

Table II. Unit square test: GDMPM iterations (GMRES iterations) to reach convergence and solution time comparison against SLEPc.

DoFs	578	2178	8450	33282	132098	526338
Iterations	3 (4)	3 (4)	3 (4)	3 (4)	3 (4)	2 (2)
GDMPM Time (s)	0.0227	0.0324	0.0874	0.3367	1.5448	4.5799
SLEPc Time (s)	0.0554	0.0390	0.1790	1.6744	6.7775	46.9862

4.2. IAEA Benchmark test

To further validate our implementation, we solve the problem by using the IAEA 2D benchmark [11]. In Figure 1 we show the mesh and its subdomains, and in Table III we show the parameters corresponding to each subdomain.

Figure 1. IAEA 2D mesh

Table III. IAEA benchmark constants

Region	D_1	D_2	$\Sigma_{1 \rightarrow 2}$	Σ_{a1}	Σ_{a2}	$\nu\Sigma_{f1}$	$\nu\Sigma_{f2}$
1	1.5	0.4	0.02	0.01	0.080	0	0.135
2	1.5	0.4	0.02	0.01	0.085	0	0.135
3	1.5	0.4	0.02	0.01	0.130	0	0.135
4	2.0	0.3	0.04	0	0.01	0	0

We produced 4 different meshes of the IAEA 2D benchmark for different element sizes and solved the problem by using the GDMPM and SLEPc, obtaining the execution times presented in Table IV. We further show the solutions computed in Figure 2, and highlight that our method yields a reduction in the solution time of up to a 72% in the largest problem. In smaller problems one observes the overhead required for the setup of the method, and thus SLEPc provides faster solution times.

Table IV. IAEA 2D benchmark test: GDMPM (GMRES) iterations and solution time for each mesh.

DoFs	14962	57256	225688	896076
Iterations	16(4)	14(4)	11(4)	9 (4)
GDMPM Time (s)	7.274	10.423	26.010	33.907
SLEPc Time (s)	1.546	5.590	32.045	116.8492

Figure 2. Fast group and thermal group results for the IAEA 2D benchmark.

4.3. Cube test

Finally, we tested our algorithm in a 3D unstructured meshes, using a unit cube. We use the same parameters presented in Table I.

Table V. Unit cube results: GDMPM (GMRES) iterations and solution time for each mesh. OOM stands for an Out Of Memory error.

DoFs	9826	71874	549250
Iterations	3 (4)	3 (4)	3 (4)
GDMPM Time (s)	0.530	6.731	37.190
SLEPc Time (s)	1.756	129.905	OOM

We observe that for larger problem sizes, the GDMPM takes significantly less time than the SLEPc solver, in addition to lower memory requirements due to the use of an iterative method. These results are in agreement with our complexity analysis provided in Section 3.3, and show that our method yields a time saving of roughly a 95% in the last effective solution of SLEPc.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

By implementing the dynamic momentum power method, we demonstrated that it is possible to significantly accelerate convergence of the standard black-box solver commonly used by SLEPc. The GDMPM does not require prior knowledge or an initial estimate of the spectrum, which makes it readily applicable to a wide range of scenarios of interest. For future work, we will look into sequential solvers leveraging the triangular block structure of the model and strategies for testing this method in large scale simulations.

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